

In natural language processing there is a preferred main conference line where researchers aim to publish, named Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL). It is commonly regarded as one of the qualitatively best among conferences.

Following the foundations of scientific research, scholars cite each other's (ACL) work when building on previous studies. The number of ACL publications and citations is seen as indicator of prestige and opens doors in the academic and non-academic job market. Consequently, researchers from the same lab or even from the same geographical area (e.g. same country) tend to cite each other, sometimes led by the familiarity of the work and its authors over its relevance. This behavior leads to scenarios in which research bubbles are formed and a foreign gaze (aside from the handful international ACL reviewers) is missing. To avoid a #like4like in the citation dynamics, are there prevention steps to be taken? How can a foreign gaze be forcefully introduced? Would this be desired?

Citing familiar and geographically close work stands in relation to citing inside the ACL conference habitat exclusively. While it might be true that a peer-reviewed paper on a top-quality conference is, in principle, more reliable than work published at, say, a newly initiated workshop, it does not mean that non-ACL papers should be ignored a priori.

Both citing your geographical neighbors and inner conference circle are forms of exclusion. How should a researcher that operates in this *safe space* and aims for high-quality references act to be more welcoming of foreign perspectives in their work?